

TRANSFORMATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: NEW FORMATS, IMPLEMENTATION OPPORTUNITIES AND PROSPECTS

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1. TRANSFORMATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

The major factors of sustainable development of the economy of Uzbekistan in modern conditions are the innovation component of economic growth, measures to intensify the process of modernization and introduction of modern technologies. To achieve this, the country has a solid innovation base, a number of scientific and specialized institutes, scientific and human resource potential, and a sufficiently high level of education of the population. The most important direction in the development of innovation activity is the strengthening of human potential.

The acceleration of innovation processes in society, globalization and digitalization require fundamental adjustments in all spheres of human activity, including education. To this end, it is necessary to ensure the development of an integral system of lifelong learning that meets the requirements of the innovation economy. Because, education is a contribution to the future, which, first of all, is beneficial to society itself. It is, first of all, necessary to work successfully, create social wealth, competitive products and have a worthy place in society. Education is a necessary factor in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation, the most important engine of the innovation process, the basis of socio-economic development of the country, its intellectual and spiritual potential. Public education is an integral part of national wealth and innovation process. Society needs, first of all, modern educated, moral, enterprising people who can independently make responsible decisions in a situation of choice, predicting their possible consequences, capable of cooperation, with a developed sense of responsibility for their country.

Obtaining quality education lays the foundation for improving people's living conditions and ensuring sustainable development. The issues of accessibility and quality of education are included in the strategic development programs of all countries of the world, because by creating an educational environment for the self-realization of the population, the state contributes to the material well-being and socio-economic stability in the country, the increase of human capital, and, consequently, the growth of its economic potential and the creation of competitive advantage in the international arena.

Globally, human capital accounts for two-thirds of wealth, with the other third being natural and manufactured (e.g., buildings, machinery) resources. In high-income countries, 70 percent of their total national wealth is human capital, while in low-income countries it is only 40 percent (Figure 1.). As countries develop, human capital becomes an increasingly important part of their total wealth as it plays a key role in the utilization of natural and other material resources.

Fig.1. Contribution of human capital to the total wealth of the country [1].

Investments in education and in the professional development of young people will bring the so-called "demographic dividend", contributing to the country's economic growth. According to experts, the demographic dividend effect is possible when the working-age population grows much faster than the dependent population, thereby increasing the productive potential, and the social, economic, and political institutions and policies of the country allow the young population to realize the growth potential created by the transition period [2].

This issue is particularly important at the present time. According to UNESCO, tertiary education enrollment in the world has increased from 18 percent in 2000 to 40 percent in 2020, and in Central Asia from 22 percent to 35 percent in the last 20 years [3]. Uzbekistan has done some work in this direction. Thus, enrollment increased from 9 percent in 2018 to 38 percent in 2022, and the number of higher education institutions increased from 84 in 2018 to 198 in 2022 [4].

The development of the education system in Uzbekistan is based on the basic principles of international educational activity, one of which is to create conditions and ensure the realization of accessible quality education. Everyone in the country is guaranteed equal rights to education, irrespective of sex, race, ethnicity, language, religion, social origin, beliefs, or personal or social status. Having achieved significant success in eliminating illiteracy and providing accessible education for all citizens, Uzbekistan retains the dominance of State funding in the field of education, which is an undoubted plus. Education in the country is realized in the following types:

- preschool education and upbringing;
- General secondary and specialized secondary education;
- vocational education;
- higher education;
- postgraduate education;
- retraining and advanced training of personnel;
- extracurricular education

Higher education in the republic is an independent type of continuous education system, which is carried out in higher educational organizations on the basis of general secondary and specialized secondary and vocational education in accordance with its legislation. There are the following types of higher educational organizations in the country: university, academy, institute (equivalent higher educational institutions). Higher education is also divided into two levels: bachelor's and master's degrees.

For the 2018-2022 years, the growth in the number of higher educational organizations (except for higher military educational organizations) can be noted in the country. Thus, in the 2022/2023 academic year, compared to the 2018/2019 academic year, their number has almost doubled (Fig. 2).

Fig.2

. Number of operating higher educational organizations in Uzbekistan (at the beginning of the academic year, units) [5]

Non-state higher educational organizations in the country carry out educational activities in accordance with state standards and requirements. In 2022 alone, their number increased by 24 units, and, compared to the 2018/2019 academic year, their number increased by 40 units. (41 times) (Fig. 3). The number of foreign higher educational organizations in 2022 alone increased by 3 units, and, compared to the 2018/2019 academic year, their number increased by 18 units. (2.8 times).

The largest number of higher educational organizations (82 units), as well as non-state ones (23 units), are concentrated in Tashkent. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya and Syrdarya regions, there are no non-state higher educational organizations at all (Fig. 4).

Fig.3. Number of operating non-state and foreign higher educational organizations (at the beginning of the academic year, units) [6]

For 2018-2022, there was an increase in the number of admissions to higher educational organizations. Thus, during the period from 2018/2019 to 2022/2023 academic years, their number increased by 2.5 times. Admission to non-state higher educational organizations increased by 45.4 times, and to foreign universities - by 2.3 times. At the beginning of the 2022/2023 academic year, the largest number of students in higher educational institutions was noted in the city of Tashkent (354 thousand people), as well as in Samarkand (84.7 thousand people) and Fergana (77.7 thousand people) regions. The smallest number of students was recorded in Syrdarya (21.5 thousand people) and Navoi (30.3 thousand people) regions.

Fig.4. Distribution of the number of operating higher educational organizations by region and form of ownership (at the beginning of the 2022/2023 academic year, units) [6].

In the 2022/2023 academic year, compared to the 2018/2019 academic year, the number of students of non-state higher education organizations increased by 72.4 times, and the number of students of foreign higher education organizations increased by 2.4 times. At the beginning of the 2022/2023 academic year, of the total number of students in higher education organizations, the share of boys (52.4%) exceeded the share of girls (47.6%). In non-state higher education organizations the share of girls (54.7%) exceeded the share of boys (45.3%), and in foreign higher education organizations vice versa - the share of boys was 65.1%, and the share of girls - 34.9%.

In 2018-2022, there was an increase in the number of teaching staff in higher educational organizations. Thus, at the beginning of the 2022/2023 academic year, compared to the 2018/2019 academic year, their number increased by 15.1 thousand people, i.e. by 56.8%. When distributing their number by regions, it can be seen that the largest number of teachers are employed in Tashkent city (14.6 thousand people), Samarkand (4.0 thousand people) and Bukhara (2.8 thousand people) regions. The lowest indicator was recorded in Syrdarya Province (0.7 thousand people).

Fig.5. Number of graduates of higher educational institutions (in thousand people) [7]

In the 2022/2023 academic year, compared to the 2018/2019 academic year, the number of teachers in non-state higher education organizations increased by 200.1 times, and their number in foreign higher education organizations - by 2.2 times. In 2022, compared to 2018, the number of graduates increased by 31.6 thousand people, i.e. by 45.0% (Fig.4). When distributing them by regions, it can be seen that the largest number of graduates graduated from higher educational organizations in Tashkent city (34.6 thousand people), Samarkand (9.0 thousand people) and Fergana (8.4 thousand people) regions. The lowest indicator was recorded in Syrdarya Province (1.9 thousand people). The number of graduates of foreign higher educational organizations decreased by 0.2 thousand people (-6.5%), and, compared to 2018, their number increased by 52.6%.

In modern Uzbekistan, higher education is one of the most rapidly developing spheres. After all, it is impossible to build a strong state with an innovative economy, a just civil society where all human rights and interests are ensured without creating an impressive talent pool. Training qualified specialists with critical thinking and up-to-date knowledge in the most in-demand professions is the primary task set by the President. The year 2023 has been declared the “**Year of Care for People and Quality Education**” in the country. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his Address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan noted that "improving the quality of education is the only correct way to develop the New Uzbekistan" [8]. Undoubtedly, this is one of the topical issues on the agenda of our country. After all, it is based on the issue of training highly qualified specialists capable of bringing Uzbekistan to the ranks of developed countries. In this regard, the fact that President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted in his Address that education is "the most important investment in the New Uzbekistan" is of deep strategic significance.

In Uzbekistan, the number of young people aged 14 to 30 is 9.6 million [9]. Official unemployment among young people is about 800 thousand people, which is 1.5 times more than the total unemployment rate. The unrecorded number of unemployed is even higher. Training of

specialists in higher and specialized secondary education does not meet the requirements of the labor market. Only 26.2% of the country's graduates work in their specialty.

Uzbekistan, along with other countries of the world, is striving to create a developed economy with high added value. The goal is to increase GDP per capita to \$2800 in 2026 and to \$4000 in 2030 in order to join the ranks of "countries with above-average incomes" [10].

As world practice shows, achieving this goal requires a well-educated and highly skilled labor force. The knowledge-based economy has increased the demand for a highly educated workforce, especially for workers with higher education, and this thesis is fundamental for a sustainable economy based on employment, innovation and education.

The primary task of recent years has been the revision of the directions, specialties and programs in which students are trained. The needs of personnel customers - objects and subjects of the economy, scientific, educational, medical, financial and other institutions - are put at the center of attention. Targeted admission to bachelor's and master's programs of universities in the relevant industries and regions is increasing. Employers now formulate requirements to knowledge, skills and competencies of future specialists, and institutes and universities have to compete in the issue of employment of graduates. Conditions for effective interaction with employers are being created in universities, and market mechanisms are being introduced in the sphere.

The credit-module system is being introduced in all public higher education institutions of Uzbekistan. The European model ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) is taken as a basis. It is a flexible process of education organization, where each student can participate in the development of his/her individual curriculum, choosing from the proposed educational programs and determining his/her academic load. This system significantly increases the share of independent learning, allows students to emphasize those disciplines that are especially important for their future career. It allows universities to constantly adjust the content of educational programs depending on the demands of the labor market.

Based on the new standards and qualification requirements, curricula have already been introduced for 625 bachelor's and 634 master's degree programs and more than 4,700 educational programs under the credit-module system. The goal is to bring the level of education in line with international standards, to enter and gain a foothold in authoritative international ratings of higher education institutions. And this is impossible without comprehensive cooperation with foreign universities.

Over the years, international cooperation in the sphere of higher education has reached unprecedented scales in Uzbekistan. More than six thousand professors and teachers of domestic universities have undergone training and internship in foreign universities and research centers in Europe, the United States, Asia and CIS countries. Local higher education institutions have attracted 6,279 foreign professors and experts since 2017.

The number of branches of foreign universities in the country has grown from seven to 31. Prestigious universities from the United States, the United Kingdom, the Republic of Korea, Turkey, Italy, Japan, Belarus, Russia and other countries have entered the higher education market of Uzbekistan. The count of joint educational programs of "double diplomas" goes into hundreds.

Cooperation with universities of the Russian Federation plays an important role in the integration of Uzbekistan's higher education into the global educational space. In 2018 and 2021, the first and the second Russian-Uzbek educational forum were held. The events were attended by hundreds of rectors, vice-rectors and professors of leading universities of the two countries.

63 "roadmaps" of scientific and educational partnership between Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation are being implemented. 115 universities of the republic are implementing 240 agreements on cooperation.

Such flagships of Russian higher education as Moscow State University of International Relations "MGIMO", National University of Science and Technology "MISIS", Moscow Engineering Physics Institute "MEPhI", Russian State University of Cinematography "VGIK", branches of St. Petersburg State University, Russian National Research Medical University named after N. Pirogov, Kazan Federal University came to the educational market of Uzbekistan. Branches of foreign universities open admission of students to those fields of education that are most in demand in Uzbekistan, but are underrepresented in domestic universities. For this purpose, joint work is being carried out with ministries, departments and leading industrial enterprises. For example, the branch of the Russian State Pedagogical University named after A. Herzen, which opened in Tashkent in 2021, has started training personnel on the order of the Ministry of Preschool Education.

The work on raising the status and incentives for teaching staff, upgrading the material and technical base of higher education institutions, building their scientific potential, etc. deserves special attention. However, even on the basis of these changes, it can be concluded that the higher school of Uzbekistan is firmly on the path of progress and full integration into the world educational space.

The funds allocated for education in Uzbekistan are increasing every year. If in 2021 the state budget allocated 2.9 trillion soums to the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education and 22.1 trillion soums to the Ministry of Public Education, then in 2022 the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education. amounted to 4.1 trillion soums and 25.8 trillion soums to the Ministry of Public Education [11].

Improving the quality of education has become one of the important directions of educational policy for the development of New Uzbekistan. In the Development Strategy for 2022-2026, much attention is paid to increasing the coverage of the population at all levels of education, since the transition to an innovation economy requires highly qualified personnel [12]. The main measures envisaged by the Strategy include measures aimed at increasing the enrollment of young people in higher education up to 50% by 2030 and improving the quality of education primarily on the basis of:

- 1) increasing the total number of higher education institutions up to 200, including non-state universities to at least 50 units;
- 2) creation of at least 1 non-state university in each region based on the region's needs in personnel with higher education;
- 3) inclusion of 10 potential universities in QS and other international rankings by 2026;
- 4) further granting academic and financial autonomy to state universities, etc.

To accelerate Uzbekistan's ongoing economic transformation, Uzbekistan needs not only to spend more, but also to invest wisely in education to ensure the transition to a knowledge economy and improve the country's standing in the international arena. In order to accelerate economic growth as Uzbekistan transitions from a commodity-based economy to a modern one, and to fully utilize the demographic dividend, there is a need to focus on improving the quality of skills learned through the education system in order to increase the country's human capital - from solid basic skills to the sophisticated skills acquired through higher education that are necessary for sustainable economic growth and innovation in a rapidly changing market and knowledge-based society. Enterprises in Uzbekistan cannot access the skills they need, and the

lack of skilled labor is considered one of the most serious constraints for enterprises. This is due to significant gaps both in the quality of fundamental education and in the labor force's access to appropriate tertiary education and training opportunities. This is exacerbated by the mismatch between the skills produced by the education system and the skills that are needed and valued by employers and are essential for new businesses in the economy.

2. DUAL HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: IMPLEMENTATION OPPORTUNITIES AND PERSPECTIVES

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 PD-5847 "On approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" important tasks in the direction of systemic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan are defined: "introduction of advanced standards of higher education, in particular, a gradual transition from education, whose curricula are aimed at obtaining theoretical knowledge, to the system of education aimed at the formation of practical skills, based on international experience, raising the content of higher education to a qualitatively new level, establishing a system of training highly qualified personnel who are able to find their place in the labor market, to make a worthy contribution to the stable development of the social sphere and sectors of the economy" [14].

Higher education institutions play an important role in the creation, dissemination, transfer of knowledge and penetration of knowledge into production sectors. To enhance this penetration, dual/cooperative higher education will be an additional conceptual solution for the higher education system in the task of providing the labor market with highly qualified personnel who can perform their functions effectively and responsibly and adapt to changing economic conditions. In Germany and other European countries, the cooperative education program is directly initiated by the employer. The student receives theoretical knowledge at the university and practical experience in the company. In Europe, this system has been showing positive results for a hundred years. Since the XII century professional organizations have already regulated the training (apprenticeship) of their descendants.

By the 19th century, this form of training had spread to other professions and industries [15]. In the 20th century, the compulsory school accompanying apprenticeship was dominated by the professional development school, which was divided by occupations and was called vocational school since 1920. Compulsory vocational school was introduced in Germany in 1938.

In the world practice we can distinguish three main models of partnership in higher education [16]. The first model - the state plays an insignificant role (UK, USA). This model of interaction between the educational community and business reflects the tendencies of decentralization of state management. The state does not formally regulate professional education, most decisions are made at the local level with the broad participation of employers. The second model - the state plans and implements professional education and manages it (France, Sweden). This model of interaction between the system of educational services and the labor market is characterized primarily by a high level of state regulation of higher education. The third model - the state determines the general framework of activities of private companies and organizations in the implementation of vocational education (Germany, the Netherlands, Denmark, Scotland). In particular, the German system of vocational education is characterized

by concentration and integration of educational resources. Cooperation between employers and educational institutions plays a huge role in the formation of a young specialist.

In France, the dual education system opens the way for students to all professional certificates registered in the national qualifications catalog.

In Germany, both public and private universities offer dual education, and their number is increasing every year. This system offers more than a thousand programs. Companies that have invested financial and time resources in the education of dual students are interested in their future employment after graduation.

On an international scale, German industrial enterprises are most actively working on innovative projects together with universities. Thus, the share of companies cooperating with universities in Germany is more than 50%, in Great Britain - 30%, in France - only 25%. According to the Mannheimer Innovationspanel research project, in 2007 there were more than 40,000 companies in Germany that maintain scientific contacts with universities. And this figure is continuously growing. German companies and corporate foundations invest more than 1.7 billion euros in research at universities. Almost half of the funds are spent on contract research, and more than 50% are spent on joint research projects.

IBA is the largest state-recognized cooperative education university in Germany, it is part of the F+U group, which has been involved in higher education for more than 40 years [17]. The university was founded in 2006 and offers bachelor's degree programs on a dual study scheme (work + study) in twelve study centers throughout Germany. To date, the university has more than 3500 students.

Dual programs are becoming increasingly popular in Germany among both students and employers. The students work in a company while studying for their bachelor's degree. This means that they gain valuable work experience during their studies and thus have excellent job opportunities in the competitive German labor market.

- IBA training programs are implemented in partnership with approved organizations that hire students as interns for the duration of their training. IBA practices a "split week" training model based on a 40-hour work week: students spend about 20 hours of study per week and 16-20 hours of on-the-job training at a partner company. By the time they graduate, IBA students have an ideal combination of academic and practical competence. IBA offers more than 30 undergraduate degree programs to choose from;
- The opportunity to study at one of 12 study centers located in major German cities;
- IBA has over 2000 partner organizations where students can find employment;

Tashkent State Agrarian University participates in the implementation of the international project " Professional Education in Central Asia - Promoting Systemic Approaches in the Food Production Sector" in cooperation with the German Agency for International Development Cooperation and International Educational Work (Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit - GIZ). This project supports partner countries (Republic of Uzbekistan, Republic of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz Republic, Republic of Tajikistan) in reforming vocational education on the example of food production sector. The main objective of the project is to improve the normative and institutional framework of dual/cooperative vocational higher education in Central Asia in the field of food production. Special attention is paid to employability orientation and introduction of international quality standards at the level of higher vocational education. The development of dual/cooperative learning, i.e. combining learning in a real working environment with learning in a higher education institution is at the core of the project activities. In addition, the project actively seeks regional harmonization and compatibility

of national vocational education systems. The project aims for its subsequent implementation at the university on the basis of the Department of "Agroeconomics and Tourism" cooperative bachelor's degree program "Logistics (for food production)". This is a 4-year (8 semesters) program with a total credit volume of 240 ECTS, characterized by a constant alternation of theoretical phases at the university and practical phases in the company and modern, practice-oriented teaching.

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Логистика в пищевом производстве (B.Sc.)
 (Фрагменты отчета)

Общая информация

1	Вузы	Казакский национальный аграрный университет (КНАУ); Кыргызский государственный технический университет (КГТУ); Худжандский политехнический институт (ХПИ); Ташкентский государственный аграрный университет (ТГАУ)
2	Название учебной программы	Логистика в пищевом производстве
3	Уровень образования	Бакалавриат (B.Sc.)
4	Начало внедрения	Начиная с 2023 г.
5	Факультет/кафедра	
6	Срок обучения (семестры)	8
7	Количество кредитов ECTS	240
8	Количество учебных мест	Бюджет определено
9	Количество студентов, обучающихся в настоящее время	0
10	Среднее количество выпускников в год	Бюджет определено
11	Целевые группы	Выпускники общего среднего и среднего профессионального образования
12	Требования к кандидатам	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Формальный доступ для выпускников общего среднего и среднего профессионального образования, определенный соответствующими национальными законодательствами Доступ к материалам определяется совместно университетом и компаниями-партнерами в части формальных квалификаций, а также дополнительных навыков, опыта и личных качеств
13	Форма обучения	Очная
14	Плата за обучение	Бюджет определена

Дата отчета: 14 марта 2023 года

¹ Akad. Assessment Report and Certification Recommendation Professional Education & Training in Central Asia (PECA). German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ). Logistics in the Food Industry (B.Sc.)

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ACQUIN is since 2003 a member of European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA) and since 2009 registered in the European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education (EQAR)

Fig.6. This curriculum is certified by the Accreditation, Certification and Quality Assurance Institute (ACQUIN).

Dual/cooperative higher education is a format of education that combines studies in a higher education institution with experience gained during internships in companies and organizations, i.e. the theoretical part of education is carried out on the basis of an educational organization, the practical part - in the workplace of the learner. The combination of higher education and workplace learning is aimed at providing both academic skills and professional knowledge. In this regard, academic theoretical knowledge gained in the classroom is complemented by workplace experience. Thus, the effectiveness of theory is tested in real life situations and vice versa. It is based on a structured partnership between a higher education institution and employers (for-profit or non-profit organizations, enterprises or public and private services).

The order of organization of dual education is determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Articles 15 and 17 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" No. LRU-637 of September 23, 2020) [18]. It should be noted that in Uzbekistan adopted the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on dual vocational education ("On measures to organize dual education in the system of vocational education"

Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan № 163 of March 29, 2021) [19]. [19].

In dual/cooperative higher education, internship experiences are an integral component of the academic program, curriculum and plan. The HEI and work-based learning phases are linked in time and content. Students receive academic credit for practicum experiences as well as support from the HEI at all stages of their studies, including during the practicum experience. The basic principle of dual/cooperative higher education is a continuous cycle between the acquisition of theoretical knowledge at HEI and the application of this knowledge in practice, in the workplace. Such a cycle allows creating synergy between theory and practice.

Thus, dual/cooperative higher education provides academic qualifications at undergraduate level, enabling students to gain extensive practical experience. It enables students to take on challenging tasks early in their professional development and helps to build a successful career. It does not replace existing academic programs in educational institutions, it is an additional and necessary format of study to enhance the higher education offered at institutional, national and international levels. If necessary, they can also be offered as part of master's and doctoral programs, under cooperative partnership and contractual terms.

Dual/cooperative higher education programs provide integrated learning (by days, weeks, months) for students within the higher education institution and on the basis of the enterprise/organization, in compliance with the requirements of the educational standards of dual/cooperative higher education (if any) and professional standards. These programs are developed on the basis of systematic/regular coordination of the educational, organizational and contractual conditions of the stakeholders, with a clear distribution of the functions of the enterprise/organization within the curriculum, including the placement of students in workplaces during the internship.

In organizational and legal terms, dual/cooperative higher education is a symbiosis of two independent (legal) units of the socio-economic system: an educational institution and an enterprise/organization. Such integration is a necessary component of personnel training in the conditions of globalization and digitalization of the economy (in accordance with the provisions of the strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030", No. PD-6079 of October 5, 2020) [20] and an important contribution to ensuring the professional competence of the labor force. Availability of qualifications in accordance with the requirements of the labor market and international standards, guaranteed level of providing graduates with jobs are important factors of employment and reducing unemployment in the country, and involvement of more qualified personnel in production activities - to improve the economic performance of the enterprise/organization.

Gradual introduction of dual/cooperative higher education in Uzbekistan, on the one hand, will contribute to raising to a qualitatively new level the process of training independently thinking highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high personal qualities, modernization of higher education, development of social sphere and sectors of economy, and on the other hand - to strengthen the role and participation of enterprises and organizations in the educational process and improve professional and communication skills of graduates (Table 1.).

Table 1.

SWOT analysis of dual/cooperative higher education in Uzbekistan [21]

Strengths (strengths)	Weaknesses (weaknesses)
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provides academic qualifications at the undergraduate level, gives students the opportunity to gain extensive practical experience, to apply scientific knowledge in practice; • high level of academic and administrative support; • pedagogical and methodological support for the student during the stages of study in higher education and in the workplace • professionally oriented training, combining study in the classroom and practice at the workplace; • tuition fees are usually paid by the partner company; • flexible response of the curriculum and academic qualifications to the needs of the labor market for highly qualified specialists with appropriate professional skills and abilities; • strengthening the learning infrastructure of the university of dual/cooperative higher education by utilizing the infrastructure of the partner company; • close connection of the educational process at the university with practice at enterprises/organizations; • emergence of new funding models. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • insecure employment of graduates; • uncoordinated policies of enterprises/organizations and higher educational institutions; • structural changes in a higher educational institution (organization of a department of dual/cooperative higher education, appointment of responsible coordinators/mentors, etc.); • organization of the educational process and redistribution of the teaching load; • the complex profile of partner companies in dual/cooperative higher education cannot always be clearly reflected in the curriculum of dual/cooperative higher education, which can cause difficulties in formulating goals and obtaining expected learning outcomes at a higher educational institution; • creating overly specialized programs to meet specific employer requirements; • developing educational programs that are too general for the needs involved; • requires a relatively high academic load on the part of the student to study and master the academic load and for practice in enterprises and/or other organizations; • curricula are too dense; • organizing payment (partial or full) of contracts and scholarships by interested parties for students studying in dual/cooperative higher education programs.
<p>Opportunities (opportunities)</p>	<p>Threats (threats)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • promotes the modernization of higher education; • the process of training independently thinking, highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high personal qualities will rise to a qualitatively new level; • expands the prospects and scope of employment opportunities for graduates; • provides a broad opportunity for faculty development through exposure to new trends, technologies and developments, as well as potential collaboration in training and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • absence or insufficiency of mechanisms for providing tax privileges/preferences for enterprises and organizations involved in dual/cooperative higher education; • financial instability of enterprises/organizations; • the small scale and narrow specialization of activities may become the reasons for the relatively low probability of concluding an agreement on their part for the cooperative (joint) training of 1 or 2 specialists with higher education, once every 3 years or 5 years;

research;

- allows higher educational institutions to increase their competitiveness and attractiveness in the educational services market;
- provides universities with the opportunity to enhance the practical relevance of the higher education they offer;
- provides the labor market with qualified personnel of the required/required qualifications;
- reduces unemployment in the country;
- improves the economic performance of an enterprise or organization;
- promotes strengthening of connections in the “knowledge triangle” - an integrated approach to policy in the field of science, education and innovation, with an emphasis on the role of universities as a subject of knowledge production;
- expands opportunities for applied research and technology transfer between universities and industry, thereby promoting innovation in the economy and in the academic environment;
- promotes the development of the social sphere and economic sectors;
- training competitive specialists in their field with communicative and professional competencies that meet the needs of society and the national economy of Uzbekistan.

- For some enterprises/organizations, long-term investment of financial resources is impractical due to a possible oversaturation of specialists in a certain profile/specialty or potential workplace in the enterprise, the possibility of obtaining a ready-made workforce of specialists from outside (i.e., there is an excess of specialists with higher education in the labor market, who are looking for a suitable and well-paid job in their specialty);
 - for an enterprise/organization, the financial costs that will be spent on training (payment for tuition at a higher educational institution) of a future specialist employee may seem unjustified;
 - there is a possibility that enterprises will refuse to cooperate in dual/cooperative higher education and long-term investment;
 - It will be a challenge to attract a sufficient number of enterprises willing and able to invest in dual/co-operative higher education and the individual student in terms of financial support, provision of human resources (mentoring) and related jobs during co-operative education.

The implementation of dual/cooperative higher education requires careful assessment from the perspective of all stakeholders in dual/cooperative higher education and their minimization in order to ensure a viable approach, including in developing the legislative framework provisions, strategic and managerial issues of dual/cooperative higher education within the framework of the concept and formulating further actions for its sustainable implementation (pilot project, roadmap and recommendations).

The objectives of the dual/cooperative higher education organization are:

1. Development of socio-economic mechanisms to support dual/cooperative higher education and models of cooperation between enterprises/organizations and higher education institutions;
2. ensuring the interrelation of educational processes of higher education institutions with the production conditions at the enterprise/organization;
3. organizing the practical part of training at enterprises/organizations and the theoretical

part at higher education institutions, involving students in work activities;

4. Formation of competencies through the implementation of educational programs in combination with labor activity;

5. Systematic improvement of educational programs taking into account the requirements of employers and their technological innovations;

6. Further expansion of participation of enterprises/organizations in certification of graduates.

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